

THE COMPUTATION OF NONLINEAR INSTABILITY FOR
MULTILAYERED COMPOSITE CYLINDRICAL SHELLS

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Abstract

In this paper, the energy method and the finite difference method are used to compute the instability behavior of multilayered fiber-reinforced composite cylindrical shells under axial compression, hydrostatic pressure, and torsion. The influences of initial imperfections, geometrical nonlinearities of shells, and physical nonlinearities of the materials on the buckling and postbuckling behavior of the shells are considered. The effect of transverse shear is also discussed. The computational results of this paper are in good agreement with experimental data.

I. Introduction

Instability of multilayered composite thin shells is an important research field in the mechanics of composite materials (1). As for the complexity of the constitutive relations of the material and the interactions of initial imperfections as well as the geometrical and physical nonlinearities to the shell buckling behavior, to solve this instability problem is very complex and difficult (2,3). Some papers reported considerations of geometrical nonlinearities and initial postbuckling behavior (4-7). For the consideration of physical nonlinearities of the material, Hahn (8) and Jones (9) investigated thin plates under axial compression.

In (10), Zhou used his method proposed in (2) to solve metal shells with anisotropic constructions. In (11), the authors used the same method to solve the instability of multilayered composite cylindrical shells and obtained good results. In this paper, we extend this method. Both the energy method and the finite difference method are used to consider not only the geometrical and physical nonlinearities, but also the influences of transverse shear on the buckling behavior of the shell. In comparison with the results given by other papers, the computational results obtained in this paper give better agreement with the test data.

II. Fundamental Equations and Solutions

The fundamental equations of multilayered composite cylindrical shells with reinforced fibers of arbitrary orientation are (11):

$$L_1(w) - L_2(F) = N_x w_{,xx} + N_y w_{,yy} + 2N_{xy} w_{,xy} \quad (1)$$

$$L_2(w) + L_3(F) = (w_{,xy})^2 - w_{,xx} w_{,yy} \quad (2)$$

where

$$L_1(\) = d_{11}(\),_{xxxx} + 4d_{16}(\),_{xxyy} + (2d_{12} + d_{66})(\),_{xxyy} + 4d_{26}(\),_{xyyy} + d_{22}(\),_{yyyy}$$

$$L_2(\) = b_{21}(\),_{xxxx} + (2b_{26} - b_{61})(\),_{xxyy} + (b_{11} + b_{22} - 2b_{66})(\),_{xxyy} + (2b_{16} - b_{62})(\),_{xyyy} + b_{12}(\),_{yyyy} - (1/R)(\),_{xx}$$

$$L_3(\) = a_{22}(\),_{xxxx} - 2a_{26}(\),_{xxyy} + (2a_{12} + a_{66})(\),_{xxyy} - 2a_{16}(\),_{xyyy} + a_{11}(\),_{yyyy}$$

$$N_x = F_{,yy}; \quad N_y = F_{,xx}; \quad N_{xy} = -F_{,xy}$$

In general, the variables in Eq. (1) can not be separated for x and y , and thus it is very hard to obtain the solution of Eq. (1) in closed form (9).

In order to find the solution of Eq. (1), make the assumption

$$F = F_n^{(1)}(x) \sin(ny/R) + F_n^{(2)}(x) \cos(ny/R) \quad (3)$$

$$w = w_n^{(1)}(x) \sin(ny/R) + w_n^{(2)}(x) \cos(ny/R) \quad (4)$$

In the case of above assumptions for small deflection, forces N_x , N_y and N_{xy} are all constants, and the right terms of the Eq. (2) can be ignored. Then, substitute Eq. (2) in Eq. (1) and compare the coefficients of these trigonometrical functions to get the following ordinary differential equations of F_n and w_n :

$$\begin{aligned} & d_{11} w_{n,xxxx}^{(1)} - (n/R)^2 (2d_{12} + 4d_{66}) w_{n,xx}^{(1)} + (n/R)^4 d_{22} w_n^{(1)} - 4(n/R) d_{16} w_{n,xxx}^{(2)} \\ & + 4(n/R)^3 d_{26} w_{n,x}^{(2)} - b_{21} F_{n,xxxx}^{(1)} + [(n/R)^2 (b_{11} + b_{22} - 2b_{66}) + (1/R)] F_{n,xx}^{(1)} - (n/R)^4 b_{12} F_n^{(1)} \\ & + (n/R) (2b_{26} - b_{61}) F_{n,xxx}^{(2)} - (n/R)^3 (2b_{16} - b_{62}) F_{n,x}^{(2)} \\ & = N_x w_{n,xx}^{(1)} - (n/R)^2 N_y w_n^{(1)} - 2(n/R) N_{xy} w_{n,x}^{(2)} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & 4d_{16} (n/R) w_{n,xxx}^{(1)} - 4(n/R)^3 d_{26} w_{n,x}^{(1)} + d_{11} w_{n,xxxx}^{(2)} - (n/R)^2 (2d_{12} + 4d_{66}) w_n^{(2)} \\ & + (n/R)^4 d_{22} w_n^{(2)} - (n/R) (2b_{26} - b_{61}) F_{n,xxx}^{(1)} + (n/R)^3 (2b_{16} - b_{62}) F_{n,x}^{(1)} - b_{21} F_{n,xxxx}^{(2)} \\ & + [(n/R)^2 (b_{11} + b_{22} - 2b_{66}) + (1/R)] F_{n,xx}^{(2)} - b_{12} (n/R)^4 F_n^{(2)} = \end{aligned}$$

$$N_x w_{n,xx}^{(2)} - (n/R)^2 N_y w_n^{(2)} + 2(n/R) N_{xy} w_{n,x}^{(1)} \quad (6)$$

$$b_{21} w_{n,xxxx}^{(1)} - [(n/R)^2 (b_{11} + b_{22} - 2b_{66}) + (1/R)] w_{n,xx}^{(1)} + b_{12} (n/R)^4 w_n^{(1)} - (n/R) (2b_{26} - b_{61}) w_{n,xxx}^{(2)} + (n/R)^3 (2b_{16} - b_{62}) w_{n,x}^{(2)} + a_{22} F_{n,xxxx}^{(1)} - (n/R)^2 (2a_{12} + a_{66}) F_{n,xx}^{(1)} + (n/R)^4 a_{11} F_n^{(1)} + 2a_{26} (n/R) F_{n,xxx}^{(2)} - 2a_{16} (n/R)^3 F_{n,x}^{(2)} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$(2b_{26} - b_{61}) (n/R) w_{n,xxx}^{(1)} - (n/R)^3 (2b_{16} - b_{62}) w_{n,x}^{(1)} + b_{21} w_{n,xxxx}^{(2)} - [(n/R)^2 (b_{11} + b_{22} - 2b_{66}) + (1/R)] w_{n,xx}^{(2)} + (n/R)^4 b_{12} w_n^{(2)} - 2(n/R) a_{26} F_{n,xxx}^{(1)} + 2(n/R)^3 a_{16} F_{n,x}^{(1)} + a_{22} F_{n,xxxx}^{(2)} - (n/R)^2 (2a_{12} + a_{66}) F_{n,xx}^{(2)} + (n/R)^4 a_{11} F_n^{(2)} = 0 \quad (8)$$

To solve Eqs. (5-8), various numerical methods and energy methods can be used. According to the energy method, suppose the deflection function w is

$$w_n = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} [A_{2i-1} \sin(ny/R) + A_{2i} \cos(ny/R)] \sin(i\pi x/L) \quad (9)$$

The function w satisfies the deflection $w = 0$ on the boundary. Substitute the function w in the equations of compatibility, i.e., Eqs. (7) and (8). Then, the stress function F_n is found:

$$F_n = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} [(B_{4i-3} \sin(i\pi x/L) + B_{4i-2} \cos(i\pi x/L)) \sin(ny/R) + (B_{4i-1} \sin(i\pi x/L) + B_{4i} \cos(i\pi x/L)) \cos(ny/R)] + (1/2) (N_x y^2 + N_y x^2) - N_{xy} xy \quad (10)$$

where

$$B_{4i-3} = -g_1^i A_{2i-1}, \quad B_{4i-2} = -g_2^i A_{2i}, \quad B_{4i-1} = -g_1^i A_{2i}, \quad B_{4i} = g_2^i A_{2i},$$

$$g_1^i = (a_i \alpha_i + b_i \beta_i) / (\alpha_i^2 - \beta_i^2), \quad g_2^i = (b_i \alpha_i + a_i \beta_i) / (\alpha_i^2 - \beta_i^2),$$

$$a_i = (i\pi/L)^4 b_{21} + (i\pi/L)^2 (n/R)^2 (b_{11} + b_{22} - 2b_{66}) + b_{12} (n/R)^2 + (1/R) (i\pi/L)^2$$

$$b_i = (i\pi/L) (n/R) [(i\pi/L)^2 (2b_{26} - b_{61}) + (n/R)^2 (2b_{16} - b_{62})]$$

$$\alpha_i = (i\pi/L)^4 a_{22} + (i\pi/L)^2 (n/R)^2 (2a_{12} + a_{66}) + (n/R)^4 a_{11}$$

$$\beta_i = 2(i\pi/L)(n/R)[(i\pi/L)^2 a_{26} + (n/R)^2 a_{16}]$$

The total potential energy of the system is

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi = & (1/2) \int_0^{2\pi R} \int_0^L (\{N\}^T [a] \{N\} + \{x\}^T [d] \{x\}) dx dy \\ & + (1/2) \int_0^{2\pi R} \int_0^L [N_x(w, x)^2 + N_y(w, y)^2 + 2N_{xy}(w, x)(w, y)] dx dy \\ = & (\pi RL/4) \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \{d_{11}(i\pi/L)^4 + 2(d_{12} + 2d_{66})(i\pi/L)^2 (n/R)^2 + d_{22}(n/R)^4 \\ & + [a_{22}(i\pi/L)^4 + (2a_{12} + a_{66})(i\pi/L)^2 (n/R)^2 + a_{11}(n/R)^4] (g_1^i)^2 + (g_2^i)^2\} \\ & - 4(i\pi/L)(n/R)[(i\pi/L)^2 a_{26} + (n/R)^2 a_{16}] g_1^i g_2^i (A_{2i-1}^2 + A_{2i}^2) \\ & + 2RL \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \{2(n/R)(\pi/L)ij[(\pi/L)^2(i^2 + j^2)d_{16} + 2(n/R)^2 d_{26}] \\ & + [a_{22}(i\pi/L)^2 (j\pi/L)^2 + a_{12}(n/R)^2 (\pi/L)^2 (i^2 + j^2) + a_{11}(n/R)^4] (jg_1^j g_2^i + ig_1^i g_2^j) \\ & + a_{66}(i\pi/L)(j\pi/L)(n/R)^2 (ig_1^j g_2^i - jg_1^i g_2^j) - a_{26}(\pi/L)^3 (n/R)[(i^2 + j^2)g_1^j g_2^i + 2ijg_2^j g_2^i] ij \\ & - a_{16}(n/R)^3 (\pi/L)[(i^2 + j^2)g_2^j g_2^i + 2ijg_1^j g_1^i]\} (j^2 - i^2)^{-1} (A_{2j-1} A_{2i}) \\ & + (\pi RL/4) \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} [(i\pi/L)^2 N_x + (n/R)^2 N_y] (A_{2i-1}^2 + A_{2i}^2) \\ & + (\pi RL) N_{xy} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} (4n/R)(ij/(j^2 - i^2)) A_{2j-1} A_{2i} \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

The notation $\sum_{j=1}^{\infty}$ in the above expression indicates the summation of j only for the case of $j+i = \text{odd numbers}$. Take the variation of the total potential energy Π with respect to the coefficients A_{2i-1} and A_{2i} to obtain the following equilibrium equations during buckling:

$$Q_1^i A_{2i-1} + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} Q_2^{ji} A_{2j} + [N_x (i\pi/L)^2 + N_y (n/R)^2] A_{2i-1} + N_{xy} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} Q_3^{ji} A_{2j} = 0 \quad (12)$$

$$Q_1^i A_{2i} - \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} Q_2^{ji} A_{2j-1} + [N_x (i\pi/L)^2 + N_y (n/R)^2] A_{2i} - N_{xy} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} Q_3^{ji} A_{2j-1} = 0 \quad (13)$$

(i = 1, 2, 3, ...)

In Eqs. (12) and (13), the notations Q_1^i , Q_2^{ji} , and Q_3^{ji} are:

$$Q_1^i = d_{11} (i\pi/L)^4 + 2(d_{12} + 2d_{66}) (i\pi/L)^2 (n/R)^2 + d_{22} (n/R)^4$$

$$+ [a_{22} (i\pi/L)^4 + (2a_{12} + a_{66}) (i\pi/L)^2 (n/R)^2 + a_{11} (n/R)^4] (g_1^i)^2 + (g_2^i)^2$$

$$- 4(i\pi/L)(n/R) [(i\pi/L)^2 a_{26} + (n/R)^2 a_{16}] g_1^i g_2^i$$

$$Q_2^{ji} = (4/\pi) \{ 2(n/R)(\pi/L) ij [(\pi/L)^2 (i^2 + j^2) d_{16} + 2(n/R)^2 d_{26}]$$

$$+ [a_{22} (i\pi/L)^2 (\alpha\pi/L)^2 + a_{12} (\pi/L)^2 (n/R)^2 (i^2 + j^2) + a_{11} (n/R)^4] (ig_1^i g_2^j + jg_2^i g_1^j)$$

$$+ a_{66} (n/R)^2 (i\pi/L)(\alpha\pi/L) (jg_1^i g_2^j + ig_1^j g_2^i) - a_{26} (n/R)(\pi/L)^3 ij [(i^2 + j^2) g_1^i g_1^j$$

$$+ 2ij g_2^i g_2^j] - a_{16} (n/R)^3 (\pi/L) [(i^2 + j^2) g_2^i g_2^j + 2ij g_1^i g_1^j] \} (i^2 - j^2)^{-1}$$

$$Q_3^{ji} = (8n/RL) (ij) (i^2 - j^2)^{-1}$$

In the numerical computation, the terms of the trigonometric series must be truncated. For shell buckling problems, the essential terms of the series are not always the terms of lowest degree. Therefore, the terms used in the computation should include those terms which characterize the buckling wave form of orthotropic cylindrical shells and in which the effect of the coupling rigidity is ignored.

Another numerical method for solving Eqs. (5-8) is the finite difference method. We use the central difference method for calculation, and in the case of shells with moderate length, when more than 50 difference nodes are used, the results are satisfactory.

Now consider the large deflection solution and postbuckling behavior of the composite cylindrical shell. Suppose the wave form of the initial imperfection is as same as the buckling wave, i.e.,

$$\bar{w}/w = \text{constant} \quad (14)$$

Take the function of the buckling wave form as

$$w = w_0 + w_1 \sin(m\pi x/L) \sin(ny/R) + w_2 \sin^2(m\pi/L) \sin^2(ny/R) \quad (15)$$

Substitute the above expression in the equation of compatibility, Eq. (2), to find the corresponding stress function F:

$$F = (1/4) \sum_{i=1}^{10} [A_i \cos m_i (m\pi x/L) \cos n_i (ny/R) + \bar{A}_i \sin m_i (m\pi x/L) \sin n_i (ny/R) + (1/2)(N_x y^2 + N_y x^2)] \quad (16)$$

Coefficients m_i and n_i can be tabulated as follows:

i	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
m_i	2	2	0	4	1	2	1	3	4	0
n_i	0	4	2	2	1	2	3	1	0	4

Substitute Eqs. (15) and (16) in the expression for the total potential energy Π to obtain

$$\Pi = (1/64) [\pi R L (m\pi/L)^2 (n/R)^2] \{F_1 w_1^2 + F_2 w_2^2 + F_3 w_1^2 w_2 + F_4 w_2^3 + F_5 w_1^2 w_2^2 + F_6 w_1^4 + F_7 w_2^4 - 4\lambda [P_1 (R/n)^2 + qR (L/m\pi)^2] (4w_1^2 + 3w_2^2)\} + \text{constant} \quad (17)$$

Coefficients A_i , \bar{A}_i , and F_i can be found in (11).

Take the variation of the total potential energy Eq. (17) with respect to w_1 and w_2 and set it to zero. Then, the equation of the equilibrium configuration curve of the initial postbuckling can be obtained as follows:

$$F_1 + F_2 w_2 + F_5 w_2^2 + 2F_6 w_1^2 - 16\lambda [P_1 (R/n)^2 + qR (L/m\pi)^2] = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$2F_2 - 24\lambda [P_1 (R/n)^2 + qR (L/m\pi)^2] w_2 + F_3 w_1^2 + 3F_4 w_2^2 + 2F_5 w_1^2 w_2 + 4F_7 w_2^2 = 0$$

The above Eq. (18) can also be written as

$$w_1^2 = [(1.5F_1 - 2F_2) + (1.5F_3 - 3F_4) w_2 + (1.5F_5 - 4F_7) w_2^2] w_2 / [F_3 - (2F_5 - 3F_6) w_2] \quad (19)$$

$$P_1 = \{(n/R)^2 (m\pi/L)^2 / 16\lambda [(m\pi/L)^2 + K(n/R)^2]\} (F_1 + F_3 w_2 + F_5 w_2^2 + 2F_6 w_1^2) \quad (20)$$

where $K = qR/P_1$. In the case of hydrostatic pressure, $K = 2$; when in uniform compression, $q = 0$ and then $K = 0$.

Eqs. (19) and (20) give the equilibrium configuration curves of the initial postbuckling. The parameters m and n denote the wave form for the classical small deflection buckling.

III. Numerical Results and Discussion

Multilayered composite cylindrical shells with constant layer thickness are computed both by the finite difference method and the energy method. In Table I, the critical pressures of three-layered composite cylindrical shells under uniform axial compression are listed. Here the material constants of the shells are: $E_{11} = 40 \times 10^6$ psi, $E_{22} = 4.5 \times 10^6$ psi, $\nu_{12} = 0.25$, and $G_{12} = 1.5 \times 10^6$ psi, and the geometry of the shell is: $R = 6$ in., $H = 0.036$ in., and $L = 12$ in.

Table I. Critical Compression of Cylindrical Shells*

$\theta =$	10°	20°	30°	40°	50°	60°	70°	80°
Ref. (4)	914.8	1114	1277	1308	1210	1081	951.8	843.1
Energy	910.8	1082	1179	1230	1216	986.6	828.2	741.0
Fin.-Dif.	908.0	1084	1212	1262	1203	986.6	820.3	733.2
n	11	12	12	12	12	12	12	11

* Compression pressure is in lb/in.²

The critical compression loads computed in this paper are lower than those of Khot and Venkaya (4). This result occurs because the deflection function w in (4) is taken as $w = h \sin(m\pi x/L) \cos(n/R)(y-\tau x)$ which is too rough to consider the influence of coupling rigidity of the shell to the critical compression. Here, in the series solution, we take the trigonometric terms $i = 1-15$, and in the finite difference solution we consider the simply supported S2 boundary condition. The results given by these two methods are nearly the same. This means that for energy method if a sufficient number of series terms is taken, the final results will be good enough for the S2 boundary condition case.

The computational results for torsional buckling of the composite shells in comparison with the test data are given in Table II. Here, in the series solution, we take the number of terms $i = 1-10$. The shell material used is Scotchply XP250, a product of Minnesota Mining and Manufacturing Co., and the cylinders are glass-epoxy preimpregnated tape-wound cylinders. The material constants are: $E_{11} = 37.92 \text{GN/m}^2$ ($5.5 \times 10^6 \text{lb/in}^2$), $E_{22} = 17.93 \text{GN/m}^2$ ($2.6 \times 10^6 \text{lb/in}^2$), $G_{12} = 4.83 \text{GN/m}^2$ ($0.7 \times 10^6 \text{lb/in}^2$), and $\nu_{12} = .37$. The geometry of the shell is: $R = 159 \text{mm}$ (6.26 in.), $L = 317.5 \text{mm}$ (12.5 in.), and $H = 0.686 \text{mm}$ (0.027 in.). In Table II, θ is the angle between the orientation of the fiber and the axial direction of the shell. The finite difference method is computed with 50 nodes for the case of the S2 boundary condition.

Table II Comparison of Torsional Buckling Loads with Theoretical Results*

Shell No.	Orient. Ang. θ			Test Data.M	[7] Series		Diff. M_3	M/M_1	M/M_2	M/M_3
	Int.	Mid.	Out.		M_1	M_2				
1a	-70°	70°	0°	10055	11434	11193	11187	0.879	0.898	0.899
4b	90°	-45°	45°	14125	14480	13811	13843	0.976	1.023	1.020
6b	45°	0°	-45°	12050	10308	11561	11854	1.169	1.042	1.017
7b	-45°	45°	90°	10135	12173	11088	11103	0.833	0.914	0.913
9b	0°	-45°	45°	9895	9925	11382	11306	0.977	0.869	0.875
11b	30°	90°	30°	10155	10823	10991	10898	0.936	0.922	0.930
12b	30°	90°	-30°	9895	11731	11000	10977	0.844	0.900	0.901

* Torsional buckling loads are in lbf.in.

From Table II, we can conclude that the theoretical results conform well with the test data. Thus, for torsional buckling, the shell is not sensitive to initial imperfections. The numerical results computed by these two methods are in better agreement with the test data than given by Tennyson (7).

A series solution is used to compute the influence of physical nonlinearity on the buckling loads of the composite shells by using a nonlinear stress-strain relation for shearing modulus given by Hahn and Tsai (12) to get the results shown in Fig. 1. In Fig. 1, two- and four-layered boron-epoxy cylindrical shells are computed. The results show that the existence of nonlinearity in the shearing modulus will usually cause the buckling loads to decrease significantly, in spite of whether the material of the shell is linear elastic or nonlinear elastic. Thus, for boron-epoxy it is necessary to consider the physical nonlinearity in buckling problems.

The postbuckling equilibrium configuration curves ($P_1 \sim w_1/H$) of [30°/-30°/0°] shells under axial compression are given in Fig. 2. Results show that such laminated composite shells under axial compression are very sensitive to initial imperfections. But, at the same time, the influence of the physical nonlinearity of the material for shearing modulus will extend the postbuckling curve to be a plain curve. So the physical nonlinearity of the material will render the shells to be not so sensitive to the initial imperfections.

The series method is also used to investigate the influence of the transverse shearing stresses to the sensitivity of initial imperfections of shells under axial compression. Numerical results show that the influence is not significant.

Fig. 1. Buckling loads of two and four layered boron-epoxy cylindrical shells under axial compression.

Fig. 2. Postbuckling equilibrium configuration curves ($P_1 - w_1/H$) of $[30^\circ/-30^\circ/0^\circ]$ shells.

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